

Chinch bugs and mealy bugs have been observed damaging rice in New Ireland, East New Britain, Morobe, Madang, and Central Provinces. Probably they are widely distributed throughout the lower elevations of Papua New Guinea.

No effective control measures have been determined, although the chinch bug is known to be susceptible to lindane (gamma-BHC). Spraying of the affected plant and of the soil at the plant's base has been unsuccessful, but seed

treatments with appropriate pesticides may be suitable. Additional studies to determine appropriate control techniques are required if the area planted to upland rice expands. ■

Rice leaf miner damage — a problem in Guyana

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The rice leaf miner was first noted as a serious rice pest in Guyana in 1975. Leaf miner epidemics have since occurred regularly, especially on late-sown crops. Recent surveys have revealed that only one species of *Hydrellia* (Diptera: Ephydriidae) (described by the author as

H. deonieri n. sp.) is endemic to Guyana and damages rice throughout the rice-growing belt. Damage can appear as a deadheart, mining, and dying of leaves on plants 7 to 32 days old. Damaged plants are stunted and less vigorous, and yields are reduced. The main reasons for the increasing importance of this pest are presumed to be a change in cultural practices (from dry to wet sowing) and the introduction of double-cropping.

Two rice crops per year are now

grown in Guyana: the main or autumn crop, harvested June–July, and the small or spring crop, harvested in December–January. Young rice seedlings that can be mined by the pest are present for a maximum of 3 to 4 months annually. A number of alternate host plants, all of the family Gramineae, help maintain the population level during the off-crop season. All varieties grown in Guyana are susceptible. In severe attacks, fields up to 40 ha have been completely destroyed. ■

An inexpensive kerosene light trap to monitor rice insects

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An inexpensive kerosene light trap tested in Philippine rice fields in 1978 is highly attractive to the following insects: *Tryporyza incertulas*, *T. innotata*, *Chilo suppressalis*, *Sesamia inferens*, *Nymphula depunctalis*, *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *Naranga aenescens*, and *Rivula nr. atimeta*. The lantern is an improvement of that presented in the 1970 Rice production manual.

The light source is a fisherman's kerosene lantern designed for outdoor use. Village tinsmiths can easily make it with locally available materials. Each lantern costs about US\$4. It uses only a few cents worth of kerosene per night and produces a bright white light. The funnel-shaped exhaust cap extends 4 cm down into the lantern body and efficiently removes the small amount of soot that accumulates on the inside of the glass (see figure). Rain does not affect the lantern's performance. The lantern, attached to a wooden or bamboo support frame, hangs above the rice crop.

1. Design of the lantern with handle. IRR I Entomology Department.

The frame has a platform that supports a basin of water (see photo). Cooking oil that is added covers the water surface

The kerosene lantern can be made inexpensively from local materials. IRR I Entomology Department.

and immobilizes fallen insects. Experience shows that baffles are not necessary. The insects hit the lantern and fall into the water basin below.

Farmers who have been taught to recognize each important species can recover and count insects daily. We are now correlating daily catches with field populations. We hope that farmers and extension technicians can use the trap as a tool in forecasting. ■